

Self Interacting Wave Fields - A Physical Wave Basis for Quantum Mechanics?

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Abstract

Self Interacting Wave Field (SIWF) theory replaces the 'probability wave' interpretation of quantum mechanics with a mass-density one. It postulates the existence of a universal acoustic wave-bearing medium in Absolute Euclidian Space Time (AEST). Places where monochromatic waves arrive with phase and direction correlated have angular momentum and are called Field Rotators (FRs). Any non-linearity at FRs makes interaction between 'structures' of FRs possible. Fundamental particles of nature arise from stable structures: where radiative losses are balanced against gains from resonance with a stochastic field within the medium. 'Phase Harmony' within the structures has Special Relativity as a consequence. The de Broglie-Einstein equations hold if FRs rotate at the Compton frequency. Schrödinger's wave function is shown to be a partial representation of the physical wave characterizing the motion of structures. Orbital and spin angular momenta are predicted to be \hbar and $\hbar/2$ respectively. The Pauli Exclusion principle is demonstrated. When applied to a 1-dimensional Simple Harmonic Oscillator and various square well potentials, the predicted eigenfunctions replicate those found via the Schrödinger equation. Eigenenergies also match if a dimensionless fractional parameter, α , is set to $1/\pi$. In 3-D this could relate to the Fine Structure Constant.

1 Introduction

1.1 History

It is nearly a century since de Broglie introduced the concept of matter waves, kick-starting a period of massive development between 1923 and 1927 which culminated in modern Quantum Mechanics. (See Pais [8] for an accurate chronology.) The nature of these waves was strongly debated at the time. Schrödinger (according to Born as quoted in Pais [8]), having elevated the concept of matter waves to produce the wave equation bearing his name, was hopeful that it signalled a return to classical thinking: "He regarded the electron not as a particle but as a density distribution given by the square of his wave function." Because

of experiments on atomic and molecular collisions, Born, in the same quote said: "(I)..was convinced that particles could not simply be abolished. A way had to be found for reconciling particles and waves." Born's view prevailed with the model of a charged point particle in a wave of probability density becoming the accepted interpretation, maybe because so many wonderful scientific and technological achievements were to be had without worrying too much about the foundations. ("Shut up and calculate!"). With nothing to support it - no structure or mechanism - Schrödinger's interpretation faded into history. Nevertheless, the Born interpretation leads to many conceptual problems - point electrons going through two slits at once; purely mathematical wave functions possessing an un-interpretable yet vitally important phase attribute; instantaneous non-physical collapse of this function; infinitely small particles which nonetheless must possess 'intrinsic' angular momentum; measurements on one particle instantaneously affecting a distant particle; a curious interconnectedness within the wave function highlighted by the path integral derivation: these phenomena have fed the 'quantum *weirdness*' industry for many years.

1.2 This Paper

This paper revisits Schrödinger's views from earlier times. One of the problems with the Schrödinger equation is that it came out of almost nothing. It was a case of 'Here is the answer, now what was the question?' Its 'derivation' was inspired by the de Broglie-Einstein equations which enabled the kinetic energy of a 'particle' to be expressed in wave terms. This was coupled with inclusion of a potential energy source term in its simplest form. Perplexingly, the solution was a complex wave function, but meaningful results could be extracted by taking the absolute square of this. Apart from the ansatz of conserving kinetic and potential energy (the Hamiltonian) it is all maths.

This paper describes a classical system for a non-point electron which completely replicates the results of QM for 1-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator and Square Well potentials. The theory is called Self Interacting Wave Fields (SIWF) and it is based on classical acoustic waves in an underlying massive medium. Acoustic waves are often treated as scalar pressure waves. In reality, the pressure changes are induced by the motion of the constituent particles within the medium supporting the wave, and thus the waves have vector characteristics. Under certain circumstances, these become highly significant and can give rise to localized spin angular momentum. Specifically, this arises where there is a relationship between the direction from which the waves arrive and their phase on arrival. This is called 'Phase-Direction Correlation' (PDC) in this paper and locations where it arises are called Field Rotators (FRs). Particles are envisioned as extended structures of interacting FRs. Thus, the angular momentum of the particle is spread (albeit in granular fashion) through the entire structure. Contrast this with QM, which is forced to consider angular momentum as 'intrinsic' to a point like particle (i.e. inexplicable!)

SIWF does not derive the Schrödinger equation, but it does show it to be a partial factor of the SIWF physical waves describing motion of structures and

the phase implications of such motion. SIWF calculations of eigenfunctions and eigenenergies are not based on the Schrödinger equation: they simply give the same results, and therefore could be seen to underlie it. SIWF theory also gives many insights into the weird aspects of QM.

2 Field Rotators

Consider four monochromatic orthogonal acoustic waves (say from N,E,S and W) in some underlying massive medium. Let them arrive at a point with phase related directly to their direction of arrival, i.e. let them be in PDC. (The phase could also be inversely related to the direction of arrival in which case the spin sense is reversed.) Animation 1 shows the summed amplitudes of four plane waves in PDC over a cell of $\pm 1/2$ of a wavelength around the node. The area of high amplitude (i.e. density) rotates around the node and so the zone has angular momentum. That this is a real effect has been demonstrated by Chengzhi Shi *et al* and others [12], [14] The torque induced on objects suspended at such acoustic wave nodes (FRs) has been demonstrated.

Now consider the nature of this rotation in terms of the centre of mass (COM) of the cell. Note that it is not the whole mass of the wave which is circulating; only the small amount sufficient to bring about the density changes. The minimum for the wave sum over the entire cycle can be considered as the zero of mass. For four plane monochromatic waves of unit amplitude a minimum value occurs at $x = -1/4$, $y = -1/4$ and $t = 1/8$ with the value $-2\sqrt{2}$. The zero for mass is set as this value and all higher values of ψ are modified accordingly. The standard method for calculating COM is used, (see for example Boas [2])

$$\int \bar{x}dM = \int x dM; \int \bar{y}dM = \int y dM$$

with

$$dM = \rho dA = \rho dx dy$$

The ρ function is the ψ value corrected for the zero of mass (ρ_0) as described above. Following through the integral gives

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{\rho_0 \pi} \sin \omega t$$

and

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{\rho_0 \pi} \cos \omega t$$

Substituting the value for $\rho_0 = 2\sqrt{2}$ gives

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \sin \omega t; \quad \bar{y} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \cos \omega t \quad (1)$$

For a wavelength of 1 these two equations represent rotation of the COM around the origin with a radius of $\frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}$. Animation 1 shows the COM as a red dot.

2.1 The Main Postulate of SIWF

SIWF is based on a postulate: not as a matter of principle but because of the very limited resources of the author. More time has been spent in finding and evaluating the consequences of the postulate than on validating it directly. In some sense, these consequences validate the postulate.

PDC results from the intersection of plane waves, each of which is the solution of a linear equation. Since the sum of solutions to linear equations is also a solution, the waves should simply pass through each other, unless of course they are made to do work locally [1], [14], [12]. The main postulate of SIWF is that some non-linearity arises because of the special circumstances at the FRs. For example, if the speed of propagation depends on the local density of the medium (a situation described by the Westervelt equation) then the rotating area of high density would be expected to modify the PDC waves. Each wave passing through the FR would undergo some degree of diminution/phase shift due to the non-linearity, but it is not practicable to follow the progress of every wave emanating from every other FR. Instead, it is postulated that the effect can be modelled by a notional spiral 'reaction' wave emanating from the FR, π out of phase with it. The selection of π is slightly arbitrary: the idea is that the reaction wave must interfere destructively with the passing wave to some extent and use of π ensures that this is the case. Note that while the reaction wave is having physical consequences, it is notional rather than real. (A real spiral wave generated from a point suffers the complication that the wave vector is not radial close to its point of generation.)

3 Interacting FRs - Phase Harmony

'Fields' of FRs are now considered. Each FR in such a field is simply an artefact of the waves passing through it in PDC but the wave field itself is continuously being changed by the reaction waves generated by all the other FRs. These 'Self-Interacting Wave Fields' are considered in detail later. First it is enlightening to consider some simple geometric results which would result from them.

For SIWF particles to exist there must be some degree of phase coherence, or 'Phase Harmony' between the FRs which constitute them, otherwise they would chaotically interfere and rapidly dissipate. The concept of phase harmony was introduced by de Broglie [3] at the birth of quantum mechanics in the context of fitting the 'matter wave' associated with the electron into a fixed length orbit around the nucleus. That aspect may remain broadly relevant, but we can use the term here more specifically to encompass the phase relationship which must exist between individual FRs within a structure. The precise nature of that relationship will be the subject of later sections. Here the assumption is that whatever the relationship, it must be unaffected by motion of the whole structure through the wave medium. To facilitate this analysis, FRs are considered as notional spiral wave emitters characterised by a phase, a spin direction and an amplitude. In this section amplitude is not relevant and only one spin is

considered.

Animation 2 illustrates the situation for a structure at rest in the fluid. The four FRs shown are in phase as indicated by the phase arrows. As each FR is emitting a crest along a grid line as indicated by the arrow, waves in the same direction from other FRs along the row are passing with the same phase. Obviously waves from diagonally separated FRs are being ignored in this argument, but it will be shown that their phase, whatever it is, can remain unchanged by motion of the structure. These are not the only locations where FRs can maintain phase harmony but that is not relevant to the present argument.

Initially we restrict attention to a row of FRs along the x -axis and analyse motion in the $+x$ direction. When the structure is at rest in the medium, should a right-bound wave crest be present at an FR, it follows that the left bound wave must be at a trough. (It will be at a crest after half a wave period when the phase arrow of the FR is now pointing in the negative x direction). This implies that the wave field along the x axis is a standing wave, and that the FRs are located at its nodes. Now considering motion of the whole file of FRs at velocity v in the x direction, if phase harmony is to be maintained there must be a modified standing wave which still has the FRs at its nodes. The wave emitted from a single FR along the $+x$ axis (which because of phase harmony, is in phase with the combined waves from all FRs in this direction) has had its frequency raised by the Doppler effect, whilst that in the $-x$ direction has had its frequency lowered. The modified standing wave arises from the combined Doppler-shifted waves.

Using the notation that $\vec{\omega}$ and $\overleftarrow{\omega}$ denote the shifted frequencies in the right and left directions gives:

$$\vec{\omega} = \frac{\omega_0}{1 - v/c}$$

$$\overleftarrow{\omega} = \frac{\omega_0}{1 + v/c}$$

Using exponential notation and the convention that a right bound wave is represented with phase $kx - \omega t$ while a left bound wave has form $-kx - \omega t$; with $\omega = ck$ the two waves can be written as the real parts of:

$$\vec{\Psi} = e^{i(\frac{\vec{\omega}x}{c} - \vec{\omega}t)}$$

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} = e^{i(-\frac{\overleftarrow{\omega}x}{c} - \overleftarrow{\omega}t + \pi)}$$

The π in the second equation indicates that at $t = 0$, $x = 0$ the waves are out of phase by π . Removing the π from the second equation introduces a minus sign.

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} = -e^{i(-\frac{\overleftarrow{\omega}x}{c} - \overleftarrow{\omega}t)}$$

The combined wave is the real part of;

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} + \vec{\Psi} = e^{i(\frac{\vec{\omega}x}{c} - \vec{\omega}t)} - e^{i(-\frac{\overleftarrow{\omega}x}{c} - \overleftarrow{\omega}t)}$$

Now let $f_1 = e^{i/2[(\vec{\omega}-\overleftarrow{\omega})\frac{x}{c}-(\vec{\omega}+\overleftarrow{\omega})t]}$ and remove it as a factor i.e.

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} + \overrightarrow{\Psi} = f_1 \left[\frac{e^{i(\frac{\vec{\omega}x}{c}-\vec{\omega}t)} - e^{i(-\frac{\overleftarrow{\omega}x}{c}-\overleftarrow{\omega}t)}}{e^{i/2[(\vec{\omega}-\overleftarrow{\omega})\frac{x}{c}-(\vec{\omega}+\overleftarrow{\omega})t]}} \right]$$

It can be shown that the second factor, say f_2 , in exponential notation reduces to:

$$e^{i\left\{\frac{(\vec{\omega}+\overleftarrow{\omega})x}{c}-\frac{(\vec{\omega}-\overleftarrow{\omega})t}{2}\right\}} - e^{-i\left\{\frac{(\vec{\omega}+\overleftarrow{\omega})x}{c}-\frac{(\vec{\omega}-\overleftarrow{\omega})t}{2}\right\}}$$

Using the identity $e^{i\theta} - e^{-i\theta} = 2i \sin \theta$ leads to

$$f_2 = 2i \sin \left[\left(\frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) \frac{x}{c} - \left(\frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) t \right]$$

Collecting the real parts and reverting to trigonometric notation gives:

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} + \overrightarrow{\Psi} = -2 \sin \left[\left(\frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) \frac{x}{c} - \left(\frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) t \right] \sin \left[\left(\frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) \frac{x}{c} - \left(\frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) t \right]$$

From here on the term 'wave' is restricted to physical objects while mathematical entities with no physical attributes are called 'sinusoids'. The combined wave is the product of two travelling sinusoids, both moving towards the right. The minus sign amounts to a phase shift of π which could be reabsorbed back into either of the sinusoids. Inspection of the first sinusoid shows that it has angular frequency which is the average of the two Doppler shifted frequencies, but its wave vector is small, being the difference between these two quantities. For reasons which will become apparent, this sinusoid is denoted as p (phase). The second sinusoid has a relatively small frequency but wave vector which is the average of the two Doppler shifted frequencies. Again, for reasons discussed below, this is denoted as s (standing). The combined physical wave is called the c wave.

The various characteristics of the s and p sinusoids can be evaluated by substitution from the Doppler shift equations, using:

$$\omega_p = \frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2}; \quad k_p = \frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2c}; \quad \omega_s = \frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2}; \quad k_s = \frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2c}$$

Results are summarised in the Box 1. (N.b.The substitution $\kappa = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ is used - this is the inverse of the more normal SR substitution $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$.)

Box 1 Non-Relativistic Expressions for p and s Sinusoids

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_s &= \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa^2 c} \\
 \omega_s &= \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa^2 c} \\
 \lambda_s &= \frac{2\pi\kappa^2 c}{\omega_0} \Rightarrow \lambda_s = \lambda_0 \kappa^2 \\
 v_s &= \frac{\omega_s}{k_s} = v \\
 k_p &= \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa^2 c^2} \\
 \omega_p &= \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa^2} \\
 \lambda_p &= \frac{2\pi\kappa^2 c^2}{\omega_0 v} \\
 v_p &= \frac{\omega_p}{k_p} = \frac{c^2}{v} \\
 v_s v_p &= c^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Notable features are as follows:

- the velocity v_s of the s sinusoid is the same as the velocity of the FRs
- the wavelength of the s sinusoid reduces with velocity by the factor κ^2 , inferring that the FRs must get closer together as v increases
- the velocity v_p of the p sinusoid is greater than c
- the wavelength of the p sinusoid contains the factor c^2/v and is very large

As the physical state is represented by the product of the s and p factors, it can be envisaged as a standing sinusoid moving with the FRs, multiplied by a phase sinusoid sweeping through it at very high velocity. This picture is illustrated later, but first, additional factors resulting from consideration of two dimensional structures must be introduced. A generalised expression for the relative phases of two FRs in a structure which has translational motion relative to a stationary fluid in AEST is derived in Appendix A. The equation is

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \gamma_{AB} - \frac{\omega}{c^2 \kappa^2} \left[\vec{l} v \pm \sqrt{c^2 \left(l^\uparrow{}^2 + \vec{l}^2 \right) - l^\uparrow{}^2 v^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

Here, \vec{l} is the distance between FRs A and B parallel to the direction of motion, l^\uparrow is the distance perpendicular to this direction, and γ is the angle between the phase direction of the two FRs. Equation 2 can be used to confirm the

conditions for phase harmony of the c wave briefly discussed above. It was shown that if two FRs are separated by a distance which smaller than the zero velocity wavelength by the factor $\vec{l}_s(v) = \vec{l}_0\kappa^2$ and phase difference between them is $k_p\vec{l}_s(v)$ (i.e this shortened distance times the rate of change of phase dictated by the p wave) the resulting phase difference should be 2π (i.e. independent of v). With:

$$k_p = \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa^2 c^2}$$

$$\vec{l}_s(v) = \vec{l}_0\kappa^2$$

the phase offset is calculated as:

$$\gamma_{AB} = k_p \vec{l}_s(v) = \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa^2 c^2} \vec{l}_0\kappa^2 = \frac{\omega_0 v \vec{l}_0}{c^2}$$

The phase difference is:

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \frac{\omega_0 v \vec{l}_0}{c^2} - \frac{\omega_0}{c^2 \kappa^2} \left[l_0 v \kappa^2 \pm \sqrt{c^2 l_0^2 \kappa^4} \right]$$

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \mp \frac{\omega_0 c l_0 \kappa^2}{c^2 \kappa^2} \quad (3)$$

Cancelling terms and evaluating this for $\omega_0 = 2\pi, l_0 = c = 1$ we have:

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \mp 2\pi$$

This is independent of v and confirms that the FRs are in phase harmony.

Now FRs in the structure which are orthogonal to the direction of motion are considered. The following conditions apply:

$$l^\uparrow = 1; \gamma_{AB} = 0; \vec{l} = 0$$

Substituting these values into Equation 2 gives:

$$\Phi_{AB'} = 0 \mp \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa^2 c^2} \sqrt{c^2 l^{\uparrow 2} - v^2 l^{\uparrow 2}}$$

With $c^2 \kappa^2 = c^2 - v^2$

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \mp \frac{\omega_0 l^\uparrow}{c^2 \kappa^2} \sqrt{\kappa^2 c^2}$$

Hence:

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \mp \frac{\omega_0 l^\uparrow}{c \kappa} \quad (4)$$

As this contains κ it is a function of v rather than invariant. There are two ways in which invariance could be obtained. Looking at Equation 4, it is clear that if ω was a function of v , say $\omega_v = \omega_0 \kappa$ it would give:

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \mp \frac{\omega_0 \kappa l^\uparrow}{c \kappa}$$

The κ 's cancel and the expression becomes invariant. With $l^\uparrow = 1$, $c = 1$ and $\omega_0 = 2\pi$ the phase difference is 2π as expected.

Alternatively, we could make l^\uparrow a function of v so $l_v^\uparrow = l_0^\uparrow \kappa$. Then we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mp \frac{\omega_0}{c^2 \kappa^2} \sqrt{c^2 l_0^{\uparrow 2} \kappa^2 - l_0^{\uparrow 2} \kappa^2 v^2} \\ & \mp \frac{\omega_0 \kappa l_0^\uparrow}{c^2 \kappa^2} \sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \\ & \mp \frac{\omega_0 \kappa^2 l_0^\uparrow}{c^2 \kappa^2} \end{aligned}$$

Again, after cancellation of κ s this shows that the phase is invariant. It is postulated that the first situation will apply because the second seems to be unphysical. It would require that the process of acceleration in the x direction caused FRs to move towards each other in the y direction. There may be a more concrete reason why contraction orthogonal to the direction of motion should not occur, but for now it is postulated that the angular frequency reduces, i.e. $\omega_v = \omega_0 \kappa$.

What does this do to contraction in the direction of motion? Looking again at equation 3 which was derived for FRs separated in the direction of motion :

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \mp \frac{\omega_0 l_0 \kappa^2}{c^2 \kappa^2}$$

Invariance occurred because the κ^2 factor in the numerator was attached to the l . However, it is clear that if one κ factor was attached to l and the other to ω the equation would remain invariant.

Summarising, based on the postulate that contraction orthogonal to the direction of motion is un-physical, the condition for phase harmony in moving structures of FRs is:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_v(v) &= \omega_0 \kappa \\ \vec{l}_v(v) &= \vec{l}_0 \kappa \end{aligned}$$

and with \vec{l} associated with the wavelength of the s sinusoid:

$$\lambda_s(v) = \lambda_0 \kappa$$

The relationships for the s and p sinusoids can now be recalculated in their 'Relativistic' form and are given in Box 2. To avoid confusion with the earlier expressions they are written with a tilde. It must be emphasised that these forms have been developed on the basis of phase harmony and have not been imposed by a Special Relativity requirement.

Box 2 Relativistic Expressions for p and s Sinusoids

ω_0 and λ_0 are the angular frequency and spatial separation of the FRs at rest. $\omega_0(v)$ and $\lambda_0(v)$ are the moving values, incorporating the postulate from above i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_0(v) &= \omega_0\kappa; & \lambda_0(v) &= \lambda_0\kappa \\ \tilde{k}_s &= \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa c} \\ \tilde{\omega}_s &= \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa c} \\ \tilde{\lambda}_s &= \frac{2\pi\kappa c}{\omega_0} \Rightarrow \tilde{\lambda}_s = \lambda_0\kappa \Rightarrow \tilde{\lambda}_s = \lambda_0(v) \\ \tilde{v}_s &= \frac{\tilde{\omega}_s}{\tilde{k}_s} = v \\ \tilde{k}_p &= \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa c^2} = \frac{k_0 v}{\kappa c} \\ \tilde{\omega}_p &= \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa} \\ \tilde{\lambda}_p &= \frac{2\pi\kappa c^2}{\omega_0 v} \\ \tilde{v}_p &= \frac{\tilde{\omega}_p}{\tilde{k}_p} = \frac{c^2}{v} \\ \tilde{v}_s \tilde{v}_p &= c^2\end{aligned}$$

Group velocities:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{v}_{p,g} &= \tilde{v}_p \\ \tilde{v}_{s,g} &= v\end{aligned}$$

We can now summarize the 1-dimensional SIWF relativistic wave equation by substituting the required factors from box 2:

$$\Psi = \overleftarrow{\Psi} + \overrightarrow{\Psi} = \sin \left[\frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa c} \frac{x}{c} - \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa} t + \pi \right] \sin \left[\frac{\omega_0}{\kappa} \frac{x}{c} - \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa c} t \right] \quad (5)$$

Results derived using equation 5 are illustrated in Animation 3 to which the following comments refer.

- The analysis leading to the s and p sinusoids is one dimensional, which is valid because motion is a vector. However, the physical situation being described is 2 dimensional because FRs are rotating extended objects. We wish to represent the phase of this rotation and we can do this using a 'phase arrow' located at the FR. (N.b The choice of direction of rotation (i.e. spin) is dependent on the relative phase of waves orthogonal to the

direction of motion. Spin is clearly an important factor but it is not particularly relevant at this point.)

- The animation illustrates phase harmony between FRs at various velocities through AEST as shown on the y axis. The x grid is in units of λ_0 which is the separation of FRs at zero velocity as can be seen in the top plot. Each FR is identified by a small arrow, with the tail of the arrow being its location and the direction of the arrow indicating its phase.
- The top plot for zero velocity shows that all the FRs are in phase. The slowly moving right-bound red line is moving at the wave propagation speed, and is located such that as it passes an FR it aligns with the phase arrow pointing right. Similarly, the smaller left-bound blue line (in a different location for each plot) aligns with a left pointing phase arrow as it passes through the FR
- Looking next at the plot for $v/c = 0.05$, the role of the p sinusoid (plotted in orange) as a fast moving right-bound indicator of FR phase becomes clear. Once again, following the red and blue lines shows that the FRs are in phase harmony and close inspection reveals that this results from the FRs being closer together and rotating more slowly, although the latter is not noticeable at such a low speed.
- The phase sinusoid is not 'physical' in any way of course - only the red and blue lines have physical reality. Nevertheless, the utility of the p sinusoid becomes more obvious in the plot for $v/c = 0.1$ (plotted in green). In comparison to the $v/c = 0.05$ plot, the wavelength has approximately halved, as has the velocity of 'propagation'. As a result, the wave vector of this wave, \tilde{k}_p , is proportional to the velocity of the FRs for non-relativistic velocities. Omitting the mass (of which more later), we see in this the core of the de Broglie equation, $p = \hbar k$.
- The lower plots show more extreme velocities. The \tilde{k}_p value continues to increase with velocity, and the distance contraction (distance between FRs) and time dilation (reduced rotation rate) becomes much more apparent. Note that the phase velocity of the phase sinusoid and the velocity of the FRs are becoming quite close, because $\tilde{v}_s \tilde{v}_p = c^2$. This has curious effects: looking closely at the plot for $v/c = 0.8$ shows that after the right-bound red wave passes through an FR, the next FR in the line rotates nearly twice before it is reached. For the left-bound blue wave, the effect is reversed: the next FR has only a small rotation until the blue line reaches it.

For an observer unaware of their motion through some underlying medium, the rotation rate of their co-moving FRs is their fundamental clock, and the distance between two FRs is their fundamental measuring stick. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- SIWF is more fundamental than SR. We have not merely shown it to be consistent with SR, we have shown that SR is a *consequence* of it. Phase harmony among FRs was the only input leading to the conclusion.
- The Lorentz transform ensures that the velocity of the SIWF waves will be observed to be the same to all observers. Einstein was able to deduce Special Relativity from the experimental fact that the speed of light was measured to be the same for all observers. The obvious conclusion is that SIWF waves propagate at the speed of light.
- The original assumption of a medium in AEST is validated because SR masks its existence. This point was made by Einstein in 1920 [4] "...the special theory of relativity does not compel us to deny ether. We may assume the existence of an ether; only we must give up ascribing a definite state of motion to it..."

4 de Broglie-Einstein and the Schrödinger Equation

4.1 de Broglie-Einstein

The analysis carried out so far has been geometric and has applied to a mathematical model for moving spiral wave structures with phase harmony. The only free parameter in the analysis has been ω_0 . The deBroglie-Einstein equations:

$$p = \hbar k; \quad E = \hbar \omega \quad (6)$$

were instrumental in the derivation of the Schrödinger equation and the theory should be able to relate to them. The missing element is mass/energy and the most plausible candidate would seem to be

$$\tilde{\omega}_p = \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa}$$

as it displays the correct behaviour relativistically. Put:

$$\beta \tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}$$

where β is a constant of proportionality, and adopt the convention that the tilde refers to the motion dependent mass. Using the relationships in Box 2, i.e:

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa c^2}; \quad \tilde{\omega}_p = \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa}$$

we can show that

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\tilde{\omega}_p v}{c^2}$$

so right hand side of the de Broglie equation can be constructed as:

$$\hbar \tilde{k}_p = \hbar \frac{\tilde{\omega}_p v}{c^2}$$

The left hand side is

$$p = v\tilde{m} = v\beta\tilde{\omega}_p$$

Equating LHS and RHS and cancelling terms gives:

$$\beta = \frac{\hbar}{c^2}$$

Reinserting this into the mass postulate $\beta\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}$ gives:

$$\frac{\hbar}{c^2}\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}$$

or:

$$\hbar\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}c^2$$

which are the two Einstein expressions for energy. They hold for all v and in particular for $v = 0$ which is the rest mass equation, when $\tilde{\omega}_p = \omega_0$ and $\tilde{m} = m_0$. Re-arranging gives:

$$\omega_0 = \frac{m_0c^2}{\hbar}$$

which is the Compton frequency for the electron.

The conclusion is that SIWF theory is compatible with the de Broglie-Einstein equations provided that $\tilde{\omega}_p$ is indicative of mass and that the rest frequency of rotation of the FRs is the Compton frequency.

4.2 Relationship with Schrödinger's Equation

Historically the de Broglie equation was a critical input to the formulation of the Schrödinger equation, providing the link between momentum and a wave, thus allowing kinetic energy to be incorporated into the Hamiltonian energy balance. It has been shown in the preceding sections that when coupled with the mass postulate :

$$\tilde{m} = \frac{\hbar\tilde{\omega}_p}{c^2}$$

the p sinusoid is essentially de Broglie's 'matter wave'. Also it has been shown that the physical c wave of the present theory is mathematically the same as the product of the s and p sinusoids multiplied by an amplitude. The latter is a vital part of the Schrödinger solutions. As seen in Animation 3, the length of the rotating arrows (i.e. the amplitude of the s sinusoid) should be used. How can the phase element be handled? In typical illustrations of Schrödinger wave functions, the complex plane and some physical direction are shown as orthogonal. Phase variation shows up as a continuous double helix of real and imaginary parts along the physical coordinate. The magnitude can be extracted as $\sqrt{\psi^*\psi}$ while the important phase is preserved. SIWF lays the complex plane 'on its back' because phase is actually representing the direction of the phase arrows at point in a physical xy plane i.e. the plane of FR rotation. The mathematics is the same but the physical picture is completely different. In

particular, the fact that the phase applies to discrete FRs at the nodes of the s sinusoid is completely lost. Quantum phase is only mysterious because half of the physical picture is missing. Perhaps the s sinusoid makes its presence felt through the otherwise difficult to explain Zitterbewegung. In 1930, Schrödinger [11] introduced the trembling motion of the point electron at the Compton frequency, deriving it as a consequence of the Dirac theory. Various authors, [6] , [13] have tried to interpret the effect based on a point electron with intrinsic spin and charge. SIWF has at its core the rotation of constituent FRs at the Compton frequency and thus presents a very obvious candidate interpretation.

4.3 Probability Density or Mass Density

Although the de Broglie-Einstein relationship for SIWF was based on the total mass of the particle, it seems very natural that the mass can be attributed to each constituent FR in the structure, the total mass being the sum over all FRs. It also seems natural that the mass contribution of each FR should be related to its amplitude (specifically the square of its amplitude). Thus SIWF must predict mass density functions - somewhat granular at the FR scale - but otherwise having the same form as the probability density functions. Although SIWF could remove many of the conceptual difficulties in QM, there remains a probabilistic element because the structures are spread through space. All the mathematical machinery of QM would be unchanged if we postulated that the probability of a particle *interacting* (rather than *being*) at some point is proportional to its mass density at that point. The words are different to the Born hypothesis, but the mathematics and the probabilistic consequences are the same. The resolution of Born's original objection to the mass density interpretation - namely that scattering results implied point particles - is not clear, except to note that nothing is more point-like than a mathematical entity, such as the Centre of Mass.

4.4 Summary

In summary:

- SIWF is compatible with the de Broglie-Einstein equations if ω_p represents mass and the rotation rate ω_0 is the Compton frequency of the particle under consideration,
- SIWF gives a natural and easily understood explanation of the 'phase' resulting from application of Schrödinger's equation to particles in motion,
- the probabilistic nature of QM remains, even though probability density waves have been replaced by granular mass density distributions.

5 Orbital and Spin Angular Momentum

5.1 Orbital Angular Momentum

The quantization of orbital angular momentum in units of \hbar was the key feature of Bohr's original quantum theory which was subsequently justified by de Broglie's matter waves. It naturally arises from SIWF as is shown below. Following from the de Broglie reasoning, integer numbers of matter waves (i.e. the p wave) must fit around the circumference of the point electron's path around the proton. SIWF has no point particle, instead having multiple FRs, which, for an electron with orbital angular momentum, must be moving around the axis of rotation in a coordinated way. Not only must the p sinusoid contain integer wavelengths, so must the s sinusoid because this simply means that FRs are spread evenly around the circumference. Thus, to maintain the phase condition, we can envisage that rings of any particular radius (let them be called necklaces) must contain integer numbers of FRs, each separated from the next by λ_s . (There is a degree of approximation because actually the FRs form a polygon and this only approximates a circle for larger rings. It is assumed that rings are large enough to validate this approximation.)

Orbital AM must arise because the necklaces rotate bodily around the proton. Assume initially that all FRs on a particular necklace have the same amplitude and thus the same mass, m_{FR} . Then we can treat all the FRs on a single necklace collectively. (There are of course very many necklaces having various different lengths.)

From SIWF it is possible to relate the velocity of the necklace to the number of FRs constituting it. Recall from Box 2 that:

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\omega_0 v}{\kappa c^2}$$

or:

$$v = \frac{\tilde{k}_p \kappa c^2}{\omega_0}$$

Let the necklace contain W FRs. Then the length of the necklace d (using the circle approximation) is

$$d = W \tilde{\lambda}_s$$

Using $\tilde{\lambda}_s = \lambda_0 \kappa$ gives:

$$d = W \lambda_0 \kappa$$

It is required that this is 2π radians of phase (or some multiple thereof). \tilde{k}_p is the number of radians of phase per unit distance, so

$$\tilde{k}_p d = 2\pi$$

Equating d 's and rearranging gives:

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{2\pi}{W \lambda_0 \kappa}$$

Substituting this into the velocity equation gives:

$$v = \frac{2\pi}{W\lambda_0\kappa} \frac{\kappa c^2}{\omega_0}$$

Cancelling terms and using the general relationship between angular frequency and wavelength for a non-dispersive wave:

$$\omega = ck : \Rightarrow \omega = \frac{c2\pi}{\lambda}$$

gives

$$v = \frac{c}{W}$$

Note that the SR equations have been used so this is invariant. The orbital angular momentum of the necklace L_o can be calculated using:

$$L_o = mass \times velocity \times r_n$$

where r_n is the radius of the necklace. We have:

$$mass = W \times m_{FR}$$

$$velocity = \frac{c}{W}$$

$$r_n \approx \frac{W\lambda_s}{2\pi}$$

Thus

$$L_o = W \times m_{FR} \times \frac{c}{W} \times \frac{W\lambda_s}{2\pi}$$

$$L_o = \frac{Wm_{FR}c\lambda_s}{2\pi}$$

To get the contribution of a single FR on this necklace divide by the number of FRs on the necklace:

$$L_{FR} = \frac{m_{FR}c\lambda_s}{2\pi}$$

The original assumption that all the FRs were of the same mass can easily be seen to be unnecessary. Also, this equation is no longer specific to a single necklace. To get the total angular momentum for the structure we can sum over all the FR masses, whatever they are and whichever necklace they are on, i.e.

$$m_e = \sum_{allFRs} m_{FR}$$

Hence;

$$L_{o,e} = \frac{m_e c \lambda_s}{2\pi}$$

This has not taken into account the relativistic increase in mass of the orbitally rotating electron, namely $m_e = m_{e,0}/\kappa$ where $m_{e,0}$ is the rest mass of the electron. Substituting for this, and putting $\lambda_s = \lambda_0\kappa$ gives:

$$L_{o,e} = \frac{m_{e,0}c\lambda_0\kappa}{2\pi\kappa}$$

The κ 's cancel, showing that the angular momentum is invariant, and with $\lambda_0 = 2\pi c/\omega_0$ we get

$$L_{o,e} = \frac{m_{e,0}c^2}{\omega_0}$$

Finally, we recognise the numerator as $h\omega_0$ giving

$$L_{o,e} = \hbar$$

and we have established that orbital angular momentum is invariant and has value \hbar or multiples thereof.

5.2 Spin Angular Momentum

Equation 1 gave a radius for the COM of a rotating FR as:

$$r_{COM} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}$$

based on a wavelength of 1. More generally,

$$r_{COM} = \frac{\lambda_s}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}$$

Substituting the expression for λ_s from Box 2, ($\lambda_s = 2\pi c\kappa/\omega_0$) and rationalizing the square root gives:

$$r_{COM} = \frac{c\sqrt{2}\kappa}{2\omega_0}$$

Let us first restrict consideration to an FR on a stationary necklace, in which case κ is 1. For a single FR, the distance, d , covered by the COM in one unit of time is given by

$$\begin{aligned} d &= 2\pi r_{COM} \\ &= 2\pi \frac{c\sqrt{2}}{2\omega_0} \\ &= \frac{\pi c\sqrt{2}}{\omega_0} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The time taken for one revolution is

$$t = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0}$$

giving a velocity for the centre of mass

$$\begin{aligned}
 v &= \frac{d}{t} \\
 &= \frac{\pi c \sqrt{2} \omega_0}{\omega_0 2\pi} \\
 &= \frac{c \sqrt{2}}{2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

The spin angular momentum for this FR is

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{FR} &= m_{FR} \times v \times r_{COM} \\
 &= m_{FR} \times \frac{c \sqrt{2}}{2} \times \frac{c \sqrt{2}}{2\omega_0} \\
 &= \frac{m_{FR} c^2}{2\omega_0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The mass of the entire structure is just the sum of the individual FR masses so we can put

$$L_{s,e} = \frac{m_{e,0} c^2}{2\omega_0}$$

Substituting $\hbar\omega_0$ for $m_{e,0}c^2$ gives

$$L_{s,e} = \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

Thus SIWF predicts that electrons in stationary orbits have spin AM of $\pm\hbar/2$ depending on their spin direction.

Now consider the case of FRs on a rotating necklace. The analysis is the same up to

$$r_{COM} = \frac{c \sqrt{2} \kappa}{2\omega_0}$$

but the κ is now left in. The expression for the distance reflects this:

$$d = \frac{\pi c \sqrt{2} \kappa}{\omega_0}$$

Calculating the time taken for one rotation raise an interesting question - should it be based on $\omega_0(v)$ or ω_p ? $\omega_0(v)$ is the rate of rotation of the FR in its own frame of reference, whereas ω_p is its rate of rotation in the stationary frame of reference, i.e. it is the rate at which the phase sinusoid passes a stationary point. A deeper analysis should involve the combined spin and orbit AMs and would introduce spin-orbit interaction. For the present it is noted that using

the rotation rate given from $t = 2\pi/\omega_p$ gives an invariant value for the spin AM:

$$\begin{aligned}
t &= \frac{2\pi}{\omega_p} \\
\omega_p &= \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa} \\
t &= \frac{2\pi\kappa}{\omega_0} \\
v &= \frac{\pi c\sqrt{2}\kappa}{\omega_0} \frac{\omega_0}{2\pi\kappa} \\
&= \frac{c\sqrt{2}}{2} \\
L_{FR} &= m_{FR} \times v \times r_{COM} \\
&= m_{FR} \frac{c\sqrt{2}}{2} \frac{c\sqrt{2}\kappa}{2\omega_0}
\end{aligned}$$

Summing over all FRs as before and applying the relativistic mass correction leads to

$$L_{s,e} = \frac{m_{e,0}c^2}{2\omega_0}$$

as before and

$$L_{s,e} = \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

In summary, SIWF is consistent with quantization of orbital angular momentum in units of \hbar and predicts that the electron will have spin angular momentum of $\pm\hbar/2$. There is nothing 'intrinsic' (i.e unexplainable) about spin AM. If Schrödinger had known about the s sinusoid he could have predicted it.

5.3 An Ugly Fact?

A strong argument for the electron being a massive point particle became apparent when Bohr found that it was necessary to calculate his original orbits around the Centre of Mass of the proton and electron in order to obtain the right energy values. SIWF and the 'necklace' model seems to imply that the FRs are distributed evenly around the proton, which would imply that the proton is at the COM. Indeed, SIWF does require that *some* FRs are to be found all the way around the proton, but does *not* require that all FRs on the necklace have to be the same magnitude. It is quite possible for the bulk of the mass to be clumped on one side while preserving the spin and orbit angular momenta. There is an interesting parallel with the de Broglie-Bohm theory [7], which adheres to the concept of a quintessential charged 'electron' containing all the mass but hypothesises that its motion is controlled by a mysterious massless 'Pilot Wave.' A SIWF solution with the bulk of the mass 'clumped' while the remainder is widespread with very low intensity begins to look very like the Pilot Wave model, except that for SIWF the 'pilot wave' and the clump are

physical manifestations of the same underlying structure which simply differs in magnitude, perhaps markedly, from place to place.

6 FRs in 2-Dimensional Arrays

So far consideration has been restricted to orthogonal plane waves (Section 2) and to FRs distributed along lines (Section 3). In reality, extended fields of FRs must be analysed. For example, in a 2 dimensional grid of FRs, waves arriving from all direction must be taken into account, not just those arriving along the grid axes. Also, structures to be examined cannot be restricted to such simple cartesian arrays (although they are quite instructive). A method is needed for identifying where particular points in space are receiving waves with the required phase/direction (PDC) relationships to exhibit spin.

6.1 Spin Discriminators

Spin-up results from a positive correlation between arriving direction and phase while spin-down is indicated by a negative correlation. The sum/difference between direction and phase of arriving waves is combined with the amplitude to form a vector. Vector summation over all arriving waves gives the magnitude of the discriminator, while the phase indicates any difference between its phase and that of the FRs in the lattice.

6.2 Discriminator Results for a Rectangular Lattice

The first set of results relates to FRs with frequency 2π placed on an integer grid in the form of a disc of radius 75. The FRs all have phase zero, amplitude 1 and spin +1. Discriminator results are calculated for test points falling within a 2 by 2 square test area centred on the origin i.e. -1 to $+1$ for both x and y . The amplitude of the arriving wave is inversely proportional to the distance from source to test point. As test points could fall arbitrarily close to FRs in the test zone, the $1/r$ calculation of amplitude could lead to very high contributions which are not physically realistic. Such contributions are excluded from the summation.

6.2.1 The Half-Wave Points

Figure 1 a) gives the results for the magnitude of the spin-up discriminator vector. It shows that there are strong areas of spin-up at the integer points within the test zone (as would be expected) but there are equally strong areas at the half-integer (e.g. 0.5, 0.5) points. Figure 1 b) shows that these are out phase by π from the integer points.

Figure 1: Discriminator results for integer FR locations only

6.2.2 Opposite Spin

Interestingly, despite all the sources being spin-up, the results for the spin-down discriminator given in Figures 1 c) and 1 d) show equally strong centres of rotation at the integer/half-integer points. (It is easier to see the points in question on the Figure than to describe their location.) As expected, the spin down discriminator returns zero where the spin up discriminator is at its maximum and *vice versa*. To illustrate the complementarity between spin-up and spin-down, Figure 1 e) shows the checker board pattern given by subtracting one from the other.

The inference from these Figures is that it should be possible to place FRs with the appropriate spin and phase relationships at all the points of high magnitude indicated by the discriminators as shown in Table 1.

This is done in Figure 2. The colour bars show that FRs in this configuration strongly support the wave structure.

Figure 2: Discriminator results for FRs at all locations with opposite spins

6.2.3 Pauli Exclusion Principle

Finally, Figure 3 shows what happens when the spin down locations are occupied by a second spin up FR structure. The magnitudes become linearised with quite high values, but as Figure 3 e) for up discriminator minus down discriminator shows, both are high in the same place (the values of Up minus Down are small but not zero - this could be because of the omission of sources close to the test area.) As it is not possible to spin in opposite directions at the same time, it can be concluded that it is not possible to have two structures with the same spin in the same place, which is just the Pauli Exclusion Principle.

6.2.4 Phase Shift

One very interesting result which can be seen from the phase graphs in Figures 1 and 2 is that the discriminator phases at FR locations are not the same as the FR phases. This is illustrated more clearly in Figure 4, which shows a cross

Table 1: Phase and Locations for Constructively Interfering FRs

	x,y	$x + 1/2, y + 1/2$	$y, x + 1/2$	$x, y + 1/2$
spin	+1	+1	-1	-1
phase	0	π	π	0

section of the phase diagram for the spin down discriminator operating on a full set of FRs (spin up and spin down) at a value of $x = .124$. Recall that the generating FRs had the parameters given in Table 1, i.e. phases of 0 and π , but the discriminator phases are $\pi/4$ and $5\pi/4$. (Red lines are drawn at these values.) The differences of $\pi/4$ seem to be geometric in origin, and the values get closer to the exact value of $\pi/4$ as the size of the field of FRs is expanded.

It might seem strange that a theory based on the postulate of Phase Harmony does not exhibit it when applied to a simple structure, in the sense that emitted and received waves are not in phase. In fact, it places a constraint on acceptable structures in two or more dimensions. For example, if the state is stationary, then the phase of all constituent FRs must change at the same rate. But a continuous change of phase is equivalent to a change of rotational frequency, (i.e. energy).

Another puzzling feature is that, at least in this rather artificial situation, the waves arising from and supporting one particular spin also generate FRs of the opposite spin - it is the same wave for both. This would not seem to accord with nature. Whether it persists as a problem when more realistic structures are considered remains to be seen.

In summary, the application of the discriminators has:

- shown that FRs in a rectangular lattice interact coherently, in the sense that FRs generating a particular spin receive significant PDC waves having the same spin;
- shown that the integer spin up lattice is not complete - FRs at half integer points with phase differing by π should also be included;
- shown that the full spin up lattice is also coherent with a spin down lattice with FR location displaced by $1/2$ a wavelength in either the x or y direction (but not both);
- shown that when both lattices are present, switching the spin sense of one of them results in destruction of coherence, i.e. FR lattices display the Pauli Exclusion Principle;
- shown that the phase received by FRs in a rectangular lattice differs from that being emitted by approximately $\pi/4$.

Figure 3: Discriminator results for FRs at all locations with same spins

7 Amplitudes

Motion of particles/structures is encoded in Schrödinger/SIWF by the de Broglie-Einstein equations, but the **form** of the structures (the Schrödinger eigenfunctions) arises from the involvement of the potential V . This has not been considered so far: SIWF must predict the same wave forms as those experimentally verified for QM. This is computationally challenging. Simple calculations show that structures such as the electron will contain many millions of FRs, and each one interacts via waves with every other one. There are strong parallels with the Feynman 'sum over all histories' derivation of the Schrödinger equation [10], [5], in that phasors from points in space are being summed. However, there are practical and conceptual differences.

- Practically, SIWF is only considering waves from discrete spatial sources (the FRs) and is only concerned with their summation at other discrete points (all the other FRs), whereas the sum over all histories considers

Figure 4: A slice taken across one of phase plots at $x = .124$. The red lines indicate phase of $\pi/4$ and $5\pi/4$

every point in space as a source and a destination. However, it is possible to see SIWF as a discrete version of the Feynman approach.

- Conceptually there is a huge difference. Feynman follows the QM assumptions that the electron is a point particle and that its position is governed by a probability wave which can be calculated from the Schrödinger equation.
- For SIWF, everything is real and physical. The FRs exist throughout the electron structure. Collectively they embody the mass of the electron and give it its spin angular momentum.

7.1 The Role of Potential

The concept of the electric charge of a point electron has been in trouble since the birth of QM. The first conceptual hurdle was eliminated by Bohr, who simply postulated away the predicted spiral decay of a charged electron inwards towards a proton. SIWF seems to take this process to its logical conclusion - the concept of the 'charge' of an electron makes no sense when considering the internal behaviour of an electron structure, although it might become relevant in an 'engineering' sense when considering effects at a distance from itself. Because of this, SIWF avoids the problems of 'electron self-energy' which plagued the subject early on. An electron structure is a unified object: it is nonsensical to consider it as a charge distribution and then to try and calculate the effects of the charge at one side on the charge at the other.

However, potential is a key component of Schrödinger's equation and must be relevant and therefore accommodated and understood. SIWF envisions particles as coherent structures of interacting real waves. With no energy source they would simply evaporate as outgoing waves carried energy away. Yet structures are stable, so energy losses must be balanced by equivalent gains, and these can only come from the vacuum. It is postulated that for each type of particle the vacuum is saturated with wave energy of the appropriate frequency (perhaps spread in some distribution because of Doppler shifting due to the motion of particles relative to AEST) and with phase and direction stochastically distributed. FRs within the structure interact with these waves non-linearly to gain energy (increase amplitude) through a process of resonance, the gain in amplitude being proportional to the amplitude itself. With this picture in mind, potential can be envisaged as a divergence in energy availability from the average vacuum level, caused by other nearby particles.

7.2 1-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator and Square Well Potentials

To keep the computation requirements within bounds, attention has been focussed on the simplest systems: a one dimensional electron in a Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential and the Infinite Square Well (ISW) potential, as both of these have analytically determined results from QM. Results for Finite Square Well (FSW) potentials are also presented. In terms of SIWF a 1-D model is poor because it suppresses all effects of phase apart from the simplistic 'in phase/out of phase' arising for FRs along a straight line.

7.3 Formulating the Problem

The essence to be captured is conservation of energy (expressed through amplitudes) in the process of

- stochastic boosting of amplitude controlled by E and V
- reduction in amplitude due to destructive interference with the reaction wave produced as the vector sum of waves from all other FRs.

In a stationary state these must balance for every FR in the structure.

For the gain:

- the relationship used in the Schrödinger equation is a starting point - essentially $\psi(E - V)$ i.e. the amplitude gains are proportional to the value of ψ with a constant of proportionality controlled by $(E - V)$. An equation of the form

$$\psi' = \psi (1 + f(E, V))$$

is postulated. The absolute gain is given by:

$$\psi' - \psi = \psi (1 + f(E, V)) - \psi$$

$$\psi' - \psi = \psi f(E, V)$$

But what is the form of $f(E, V)$? In Schrödinger's equation it is simply $(E - V)$ and the solutions identify the points where $E = V$ as points of inflection between the negative curvature (sinusoidal) and the positive curvature (inverse exponential) zones. However, ψ can be non-zero at these points so for SIWF there must be gains and $(E - V)$ cannot be used. There must be an additional constant underlying potential at all points - the vacuum potential, say V_v . Without this potential, structures would simply evaporate, and its presence resolves the issue of no gain for $E = V$. The modified gain function is:

$$f(E, V(x)) = V_v + E - V(x)$$

(N.b. V_v could be written as negative. It is written as positive in this expression and results subsequently show it to have negative value.)

For the losses:

- The destructive interference losses are not proportional to the value of ψ in question - they result from the sum of the reaction waves arriving from every other FR. Factors to be considered are:
 - the reaction coefficient - taken to be the dimensionless ratio of reaction wave amplitude to FR amplitude.
 - a dimensionless constant relating the amplitude at unit distance from the FR to the notional amplitude of the FR. (Subsequent received amplitudes fall off harmonically i.e. $1/2, 1/3, 1/4, 1/5...$)
 - In modelling SIWF, these constants cannot be distinguished and they are grouped together as a single entity α which is now the ratio of the amplitude of the reaction wave at distance λ_s from the FR node to the amplitude of the FR itself.
- the summed contributions Σ must be negated because they are π out of phase with the FRs

Thus

$$Gains + (-\Sigma) = 0$$

i.e.

$$Gains = \Sigma$$

Taking these considerations into account, the stationary state SIWF equation becomes:

$$\psi(V_v + E - V(x)) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_n \alpha}{n \Delta x} + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{-1} \frac{\psi_n \alpha}{-n \Delta x}$$

Rearranging and shortening the right hand terms to Σ :

$$\psi(V_v - V(x)) - \Sigma = -E\psi$$

$$\psi (V (x) - V_v) + \Sigma = E\psi$$

This can be implemented in matrix form (with $\Delta x = 1$) as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_1 - V_v & \alpha & \alpha/2 & \alpha/3 & \dots \\ \alpha & V_2 - V_v & \alpha & \alpha/2 & \alpha/3 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \alpha/3 & \alpha/2 & \alpha & V_{N-1} - V_v \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_1 \\ \psi_2 \\ \dots \\ \psi_{N-1} \end{bmatrix} = E \begin{bmatrix} \psi_1 \\ \psi_2 \\ \dots \\ \psi_{N-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrices represent a set of non-sparse simultaneous equations which can be solved efficiently using Python, Numpy and Scipy. (The Python program SIWF1DPublic.py is available to replicate these results.)

7.4 SHO Results

At first sight it is a somewhat forlorn hope that equations based on the summation of the harmonic series (which does not converge) could ever be compatible with QM, even given that the terms are multiplied by some other function which does converge. However, when the equations are solved the form of the squared eigenfunctions is identical to QM. To provide a comparison, typical

Figure 5: Results for $N = 2000$ and $V(y) = 10^5 (y - 1/2)^2$

QM solutions for an SHO potential are given in Figure 5 which shows selected eigenfunctions produced using an openly available program [9]. Compare the SIWF results given in Figure 6 (parameters chosen to allow qualitative comparison with Figure 5.) The numerical values for the energies differ of course, because the results in Figure 5 are based on a normalized length of 1, whilst the unit of length in the SIWF results is λ_s i.e. the wavelength.

An insight into how this could happen is gained from the results for ψ in Figure 7. The ψ values at adjacent FRs are alternatively positive and negative! In the context of the 1D model, this implies that the phases of adjacent FRs

Figure 6: SIWF results for ψ^2 . Compare with Figure 5

Figure 7: ψ Close up of first Eigenfunction showing sign alternation.

Figure 8: SIWF results showing linearity of energies.

differ by π . This is a rather counter-intuitive result but represents a potentially real physical scenario nonetheless. It would seem that all the potential infinities resulting from the harmonic series approximately cancel themselves out, and what remains is coincident with the solution to Schrödinger's equation. Nature has chosen the convergent alternating harmonic series in place of the non-convergent harmonic series.

Finally, in Figure 8 the equal spacing of the energy levels is shown. Two factors are relevant to this graph:

- while ΔE is constant and dependent only on a and C , the value of the first energy level depends on the value of V_v used in the calculation. The program automatically adjusts the value of V_v to give the first two energies the ratio of 1 to 3. Justification for this is given in Section 7.4.1 below.
- it is fortuitous that the values of the parameters a and C used in the calculation happen to give rise to round number energies.

7.4.1 Energy Levels and V_v

For fixed values of α and C the eigenenergies depend on the value of V_v . Figure 9 shows the lower eigenenergies obtained for various values of the SHO constant C with V_v set at zero and $\alpha = 1/137$ (perhaps whimsically!). The crosses are data points and the lines are best fit linear regression. The lines intersect at -0.5 with an energy of -0.01011894 . This implies that the first energy eigenfunction is at $1/2$ a unit above some zero of energy and subsequent values fall at $3/2, 5/2...$ as expected for SHO.

Results for the Infinite Square Well are mainly discussed below, but it is constructive at this point to compare Figure 9 with Figure 10 which plots similar results for $V_v = 0$ and $\alpha = 1/137$ for an Infinite Square Well (IFS). In this case

Figure 9: SHO Eigenenergies vs n for $V_v = 0$, $\alpha = 1/137$ and various C values

Figure 10: ISW Eigenenergies vs n for $V_v = 0$, $\alpha = 1/137$ and various well widths

Figure 11: Relationship between ΔE and $\sqrt{(C\alpha)}$

the parameter is the width of the well. As before, the points are data points while in this case the lines are best fit of the form $E = an^2 + b$, because the theoretical QM result has $E_n \propto n^2$. The value of the 'zero' of energy is again -0.01011894 but in this case, the first eigenenergy falls at $n=1$, fitting the QM pattern 1, 4, 9... It is concluded that adjusting V_v so that the ratios of the first two energies is as predicted by QM is justified because the correct ratios exist in the unadjusted results.

7.4.2 Aligning SHO Results With QM

While the form of the eigenfunctions clearly match those for the Time Independent Schrödinger Equation (TISE), they are not numerically consistent. The independent variables are α and C . (N is not a variable in SIWF theory: the fundamental length is λ_s and N is merely a spatial range for the calculation.) In order to establish the correct numerical relationship, solutions for a range of C and α values have been calculated. Results are examined in Figure 11. A plot of ΔE against $\sqrt{C\alpha}$ proves to be linear and is fitted by a line passing through the origin with slope 0.70719. This is $1/\sqrt{2}$ to four significant figures, and is taken to be this exact value in further work i.e the empirical expression for ΔE is:

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha C}{2}}$$

The empirical equation for ΔE is not dimensionally correct. Since the results for QM are known analytically, they can be used to rectify this. From QM:

$$\omega_0 = \sqrt{\frac{C}{m_e}}$$

(where m_e is the electron mass) and

$$\Delta E = \hbar\omega_0$$

whence

$$\Delta E_{QM} = \hbar\sqrt{\frac{C}{m_e}}$$

Setting the empirical expression for ΔE equal to the QM expression and noting that this α is empirical by writing α_e gives:

$$\sqrt{\frac{\alpha_e C}{2}} = \hbar\sqrt{\frac{C}{m_e}}$$

Squaring and cancelling the C 's gives:

$$\alpha_e = \frac{2\hbar^2}{m_e}$$

Within SIWF theory, α has been defined as a dimensionless ratio, while as written, (with \hbar having dimensions $[ML^2T^{-1}]$), α_e has dimensions

$$[\alpha_e] = [ML^4T^{-2}]$$

which is equivalent to

$$\left[ML^2T^{-1} \times L \times \frac{L}{T} \right]$$

This can be recognised as an angular momentum, a length and a velocity. The angular momentum was introduced from the QM side of the ΔE comparison and is therefore \hbar . The SIWF solution sets the distance between FRs as 1, and the speed of wave propagation as 1 so the dimensions of these have been ignored in deriving the empirical expression. The wavelength for a stationary particle is:

$$\lambda_s = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega_e}$$

and

$$\frac{L}{T} = c$$

Let us write

$$\alpha_e = \alpha_d[\hbar\lambda_s c]$$

where α_d is the dimensionless reaction coefficient and the square brackets hold a term having the correct dimensions. Let this term actually be $\hbar\lambda_s c$:

$$\alpha_e = \alpha_d \hbar \lambda_s c$$

Then we have

$$\alpha_d \hbar \lambda_s c = \frac{2\hbar^2}{m_e}$$

Figure 12: SHO Relationship between V_v and α

Upon substitution for λ_s and in turn ω_e this reduces to

$$\alpha_d = \frac{1}{\pi}$$

Figure 12 shows the relationship of V_v against C and α . V_v is independent of C and is linearly related to α with slope -1.3863. This value can be explained because the solutions found are based on the alternating harmonic series which is known to converge to $\ln 2 = 0.693147$. FRs are receiving the reaction wave from the right and from the left, each being a summed alternating harmonic sequence (albeit multiplied by the ψ function) and the contributions thus scale to $2 \ln 2 = 1.38629$.

Figure 13: First four Infinite Square Well ψ^2 , Well width = 500, Wall height = 1, $\alpha = 1/137$

Figure 14: Infinite Square Well energies, Well width = 500, Wall height = 1, $\alpha = 1/137$

7.5 Square Well Results

Solutions for square well potentials are calculated in the same way as for SHO, but with $V(x)$ modified as required. Figures 13 and 14 show typical results for the Infinite Square Well. (n.b.'Infinite' means the wall potential is increased until there is no further change in any of the lower eigenenergies.) The solutions are confined within the well, and (as previously identified in Figure 10), the energies are proportional to n^2 .

7.5.1 Aligning Infinite Square Well Results with QM

In a similar fashion as applied to SHO, results have been calculated for a broad range of the parameters. Figure 15 shows that the relationship between α and V_v is the same as that for the SHO potential given in Figure 12. Figure 16 shows the full relationship for all three variables. The empirical relationship can be read from this Figure as

$$\frac{\sqrt{(\alpha)}}{\sqrt{(E_1)}} = 0.6366W$$

The numeric factor is $2/\pi$ and is taken to be this exact value:

$$\frac{\sqrt{(\alpha_e)}}{\sqrt{(E_1)}} = \frac{2W}{\pi}$$

So empirically,

$$E_{1(SIWF)} = \frac{\alpha_e \pi^2}{4W^2}$$

Figure 15: Relationship between V_v and α for Infinite Square Well

Figure 16: Relationship between $\sqrt{\alpha/E}$ and Well Width for all α

W is a composite of a dimensionless number, say W_n , being the number of integer wavelengths in the well multiplied by the wavelength λ_s .

$$W = n\lambda_s$$

It has dimensions $[L]$. As in Section 7.4.2, dimensionally:

$$[\alpha_e] = [ML^2T^{-2}][L^2]$$

$$[\alpha_e] = [ML^4T^{-2}] \equiv \left[ML^2T^{-1} \times L \times \frac{L}{T} \right]$$

and we can try

$$\alpha_e = \alpha_d \hbar c \lambda_s$$

The value of the the lowest energy level for the ISW is known from QM to be

$$E_{1(QM)} = \frac{\pi^2 \hbar^2}{2m_e a^2}$$

where a is the width of the well. Equating the QM and SIWF energies:

$$\frac{\pi^2 \hbar^2}{2m_e a^2} = \frac{\alpha_d \pi^2 c \lambda_s \hbar}{4W^2}$$

Using the substitutions

$$\lambda_s = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega_e}; \quad \omega_e = \frac{m_e c^2}{\hbar}; \quad a = W_n \lambda_s$$

reduces the LHS to

$$\frac{m_e c^2}{8W_n^2}$$

Similarly, the RHS reduces to

$$\frac{\alpha_d m_e c^2 \pi}{8W_n^2}$$

whence

$$\alpha_d = \frac{1}{\pi}$$

which is the same value as for the SHO case.

7.5.2 Finite Square Well

A Finite Square Well results from reduction in the height of the wall potential and is illustrated in Figures 17 and 18. With the illustrative parameters given, the first two energy states are bound, whilst the third and fourth are not. First and second levels rise somewhat like the ISW energies, but the third and fourth do not follow the rule. These higher energies are spurious and reflect that the method of calculation leads to structures not bound by the well becoming bound by the spatial limits of the calculation as is clear from Figure 17.

Figure 17: First four Finite Square Well ψ^2 , Well width = 500, Wall height = $3e - 7$, $\alpha = 1/137$

7.6 Summary

- Despite the 1-D model suppressing important features of SIWF, it has been shown to be capable of giving identical results to the Schrödinger equation for SHO, IFS and FSW potentials, provided the α parameter is set to $1/\pi$. There is every reason to think that the value of α would be much lower for full three dimensional models. This is because the 1-D model is calculating the gain in full, but the destructive interference loss is being limited to two directions.
- SIWF calculations reflect an underlying physical structure and do not introduce Schrödinger's equation 'by stealth'. The fact that the results are identical implies that SIWF is the reason Schrödinger's equation works, rather than the other way round.
- The Fine Structure Constant pervades QM but has no theoretical basis. SIWF requires a small dimensionless parameter which has a physical interpretation and is, at least in principle, calculable.

8 Discussion and Speculation

SIWF has a long way to go. If successful it must be able to replicate all the detailed findings of QM such as the splitting of energy levels. Unfortunately moving on to 2 and 3 dimensions is computationally challenging. Meanwhile, more can perhaps be achieved in the same vein as the calculation of spin and orbit angular momentum - by identifying some essential feature and generalising.

Because the conceptual differences between SIWF and conventional QM are so large they throw up many opportunities for speculation. Some of these are now discussed briefly.

Figure 18: Finite Square Well energies, Well width = 500, Wall height = $3e - 7$, $\alpha = 1/137$

8.1 Internal Kinetic Energy

The insistence that particles are point-like has denied the possibility of them having a classical internal kinetic energy. Instead they have mass which is interpreted as being an intrinsic energy, related to some inexplicable frequency via $\hbar\omega = mc^2$. SIWF should give access to a real and calculable internal KE (IKE). This seems to open the door to a more comprehensible basis for forces. For example, consider gravity. Physics assigns a 'gravitational potential' to matter. A particle at rest has zero external KE, but because of its additional gravitational potential it can accelerate and accumulate external KE by falling. General Relativity predicts, and experiments confirm, that clocks run more slowly in higher gravitational fields. For SIWF, this would be interpreted as a lower rate of FR rotation, and consequently a lower internal KE. The 'force' of gravity could then be encapsulated in the notion that particles always seek to minimize their IKE.

This idea might be extended to electrical potential. SIWF has replaced the point charge with the notion that 'charged' particle structures modify the surrounding vacuum energy field. The inference is that structures which 'feel' each other are sharing access to the same frequency field in some way. If the electron vacuum field is characterized by a particular frequency, then the proton field must enhance it. It could be that although the proton's constituent quarks have a different vacuum field frequency, they are permanently in motion with respect to it and Doppler shifted waves leaking from them overlap the electron frequency. Because of the thermal motion of matter, the spectrum of the vacuum field of the electron must be smeared rather than sharp. Boosting and similar smearing of the field by the proton would mean that some lower frequency element became sufficiently intense to support the electron, which could thus

minimize its IKE. Such effects would still be quantized.

8.2 FRagments

- Dark Matter

SIWF is based on structures which are sustained by resonating with components of a stochastic vacuum wave field that is 'saturated' (in the sense that if it was any more intense additional electrons could form and reduce its intensity.) Because it is stochastic, it follows that clumps (let us call them 'FRagments') of interacting FRs must be arising and dispersing continually throughout space. If FRagments feel the frequency gradient of gravity during their brief existence, on the principle of minimizing IKE they would accelerate towards the source of the field, in so doing carrying energy with them. The energy density in the stochastic field might thus be increased in areas where large masses exist, and FRagment intensity might be increased there. Dark matter is an unsolved riddle in astrophysics. Various candidates have been proposed and SIWF offers another. If FRagments add to the gravitational field as well as feeling it, the consequences would be observable as Dark Matter.

- Electromagnetism

All the mathematical machinery exists to calculate the effects of electromagnetism, yet at the deepest level it remains a mystery. Initially there was an ether to support electromagnetic waves, then Special Relativity 'banished' the ether, a state which persists in public perception, despite Einstein himself repudiating it a century ago [4]. Then there was the 'vacuum', which was nevertheless required to exhibit physical properties. SIWF FRagments offer an interesting alternative. If FRagments are all-pervasive they could participate in wave propagation. For example, consider an electron being forced to oscillate along an antenna. Whilst moving, the rate of rotation of its FRs will be reduced and this lower clock rate would be impressed on the stochastic vacuum field. FRagments could react to this gradient and accelerate towards it, but in so doing could create their own orthogonal clock rate gradient and so on in a propagating wave. The physical characteristics of the vacuum required for classical electromagnetism could thus be based on the behaviour of FRagments.

8.3 Structures

Apart from Section 5 the form of possible structures has been barely touched upon. Effort has been concentrated on showing that the framework of SIWF is compatible with QM. If the theory is to underlie all matter, what are the structures and how do their differences lead to such a vast range of physical characteristics? The Standard Model does not really give answers: there are too many free parameters. SIWF has no answers yet but at least it offers a glimmer of hope that such answers might exist. One signpost is that Phase Harmony

structures can be based on both rectangular grids and triangular grids. Those based on triangular grids can be classified as having the same spin at all vertices, or one spin different from the other two. There are echoes of quark structures here.

A Phase Harmony Equation for FR Structures with Translational Motion

Figure 19: Model for FRs with fixed spatial relationships moving through AEST

Consider the situation illustrated in Figure 19. There are two Field Rotators A and B within a structure that is moving to the right through AEST with velocity v . The rotational phase of A and B are indicated by the direction of the associated arrows viewed as clock hands (rotating anti-clockwise to observe the mathematical convention for the measurement of angles). Let the phase of the two FRs at a fixed time differ by the angle γ . Let \vec{l} be the distance between A and B parallel to the direction of motion, and l^\uparrow be the distance perpendicular to this direction. To calculate the relative phase of the wave from A arriving at B' we need to find the time, Δt , taken for the wave to travel the distance AB' . We have:

$$c^2 \Delta t^2 = l^{\uparrow 2} + (\vec{l} + v\Delta t)^2$$

Re-arranging gives the quadratic in Δt :

$$\Delta t^2 - \Delta t \frac{2\vec{l}v}{(c^2 - v^2)} - \frac{(l^{\uparrow 2} + \vec{l}^2)}{c^2 - v^2}$$

Solving for Δt and putting $\kappa = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ gives:

$$\Delta t = \frac{1}{c^2 \kappa^2} \left[\vec{l} v \pm \sqrt{c^2 \left(l^{\uparrow 2} + \vec{l}^2 \right) - l^{\uparrow 2} v^2} \right]$$

Knowing this time the phase difference between B' and B can be calculated. It is $-\omega \Delta t$ (minus because B is at an earlier time than B'), where ω is the angular frequency of the FRs at this velocity. Since the phase difference between A and B is γ_{AB} , the total phase difference is

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \gamma_{AB} - \omega \Delta t$$

Hence:

$$\Phi_{AB'} = \gamma_{AB} - \frac{\omega}{c^2 \kappa^2} \left[\vec{l} v \pm \sqrt{c^2 \left(l^{\uparrow 2} + \vec{l}^2 \right) - l^{\uparrow 2} v^2} \right]$$

which is the required general equation.

References

- [1] Konstantin Y. Bliokh and Franco Nori. Spin and orbital angular momenta of acoustic beams. *Phys. Rev. B*, 99:174310, May 2019.
- [2] Mary L Boas. *Mathematical methods in the physical sciences*. John Wiley & Sons, 2006.
- [3] Louis De Broglie. Waves and quanta. *Nature*, 112(2815):540–540, 1923.
- [4] Albert Einstein. *Sidelights on Relativity*. Dover, 1983.
- [5] Richard P Feynman and Albert R Hibbs. *Quantum mechanics and path integrals*. McGraw-Hill, 1965.
- [6] David Hestenes. The zitterbewegung interpretation of quantum mechanics. *Foundations of Physics*, 20(10):1213–1232, 1990.
- [7] Peter R Holland. *The quantum theory of motion: an account of the de Broglie-Bohm causal interpretation of quantum mechanics*. Cambridge university press, 1995.
- [8] Abraham Pais. Inward bound: On matter and forces in the physical world, 1986.
- [9] Luke Polson. Eigenstates of any 1d potential, youtube channel, mr p solver, 2021.
- [10] P Richard. Feynman. qed: The strange theory of light and matter, 1985.
- [11] E. Schrodinger. *Sitzungber. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.Phys.-Math.KL.*, 24:418, 1930.
- [12] Chengzhi Shi, Rongkuo Zhao, Yang Long, Sui Yang, Yuan Wang, Hong Chen, Jie Ren, and Xiang Zhang. Observation of acoustic spin. *National Science Review*, 6(4):707–712, 2019.
- [13] Burra G Sidharth. Revisiting zitterbewegung. *International Journal of Theoretical Physics*, 48(2):497–506, 2009.
- [14] Karen Volke-Sepúlveda, Arturo O Santillán, and Ricardo R Boullosa. Transfer of angular momentum to matter from acoustical vortices in free space. *Physical review letters*, 100(2):024302, 2008.